

(Pre)Planning the Handling of Research Data in Antiquities for the Entire Life Cycle

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Aim of this paper

In the antiquities, generic handouts for quality assurance of digital data throughout the data lifecycle are a desideratum. This paper aims to describe requirements that are generic to the quality of research data in this field from the perspective of archiving, accessibility, and reuse.

Introduction

Sustainable data management of antiquities data is a dynamic process. It must be considered and implemented from the beginning of project planning. Archaeological documentation, (finds) materials, and digital information contribute to the sum of human knowledge about the past and are selected for archiving, retrieval, and subsequent use during the course of a project. Research data should be managed based on the guidelines presented here and, where appropriate, according to more detailed international, national, regional, or institutional regulations. Management of data throughout its life cycle, up to and including planning for transfer to an appropriate long-term repository, should not occur near or after the end of a project, for these are key processes for protecting, preserving, and providing accessibility to all components of an archaeological archive from the outset. (adapted from: Perrin et. al: "Archaeological Archiving in Europe: A Handbook" EAC Guidelines 1, Namur 2012, p. 19).

(Research) data management in this sense always takes place with the goal of preserving data quality and useability for the future. This includes the implementation of **FAIR** and **CARE** principles and involves not only the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability (FAIR) of an antiquarian dataset, but also its political-legal, cultural, ethical and social dimensions (CARE).

1) Access & data protection

The question as to which data are protected by **copyright** or fall under data **protection guidelines** is often not easy to answer at the beginning of a project. Nevertheless, requirements for and restrictions on publishing data should be checked at an early stage. Only then can a decision be made as to which **license** should be used to make data available to third parties and how **intellectual property rights** should be documented. Without this information, legally compliant (re-)use is impossible. Both archiving data completely openly as well as completely closed are conceivable and it is necessary to identify which actions are permitted with the published data. Often rules and regulations stipulated by Institutions, project sponsors, funding agencies (e.g. **DFG**), responsible state offices or (inter)national project participants must be observed. It may also be necessary to make certain data **anonymous** or unrecognizable (e.g. coordinates). To comply both with legal requirements and the concept of open science, data provision should follow the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary".

2) Data formats & data quality

Which data formats are used or generated? This can and should be aligned with subject-specific recommendations (e.g. **IANUS**, **VLA**) at an early stage. Ideally, all formats should be **open** and **non complex**. If, for a valid reason, proprietary software and formats must be used, it must be clear into which format these can be exported, as loss-free as possible, for archiving or publication. Project-internal criteria for **data quality**, subject-specific guidelines and data archiving specifications of data repositories should be taken into account and implemented at an early stage.

3) Metadata, Standards & Policies

All data should be described in such a way that it remains readable and understandable over the long term. Decisions should be made about what information is needed to **document** the research data and at what point this documentation should happen. There are numerous and differently defined **metadata standards**. Which one to choose and how the metadata is stored will often be determined by the **infrastructure chosen**. Also, the **data policy** of the data-producing institution must be followed and requirements for **unique identification** must be clarified. Machine readability should always be an aim when choosing standards and norm data.

4) Data organization & documentation

Rules should be established for **naming, sorting, and versioning** files. **Directory structures** should be logical, comprehensible and self-explanatory. Media breaks, i.e., a jump from one medium to another during data transfer, should be avoided as far as possible. Data storage should always be documented. **Strategies for storage and backup** should be defined and a responsible person, who is appropriately qualified, should be assigned with data management. This applies both to data **suitable** for future reuse and data for archiving, as well as to data of temporary interest during a project lifecycle.

5) Infrastructure

Suitable infrastructure providers, ideally certified, for **archiving** or publication should be selected and contacted at an early stage in order to attain information on the data specifications to be followed. Consideration should be given to whether an existing institutional infrastructure can be used to organize, manage, and store the data. This also depends on the expected **total data volume** generated during the duration of the project. While this may be difficult to estimate at the outset, it is necessary to at least make an approximate estimate as this may have implications for data storage and backup.

A **data management plan** is mandatory. This can and should be adapted during the course of the project to support **dynamic research data management** during the research process.